

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THE BOND BEHAVIOR OF CFRP-TO-CONCRETE INTERFACE UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

An experimental program is conducted to investigate the bond fatigue behavior of CFRP-to-concrete bonded specimens. The fatigue performance of two different CFRP composite types including laminate versus fabric sheet is evaluated through the examination of bond-slip relationship and strain response. Also, four various bond lengths are considered in each EB-CFRP configuration (laminate vs. sheet) and the bond behavior is evaluated with respect to this variable. Results from this study show that using CFRP fabric sheet can provide a better tool for strengthening concrete structures under fatigue loading in comparison with CFRP laminate, in terms of fatigue life and residual capacity.

KEYWORDS

Fatigue behavior; CFRP-to-concrete interface; CFRP laminate; CFRP fabric sheet; Bond-slip relationship; Cyclic loading.

INTRODUCTION

Strengthening reinforced concrete (RC) structures via externally bonded (EB) fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) techniques has been widely approved by researchers in the field of construction engineering. The exceptional properties of carbon FRP (CFRP) composites to withstand fatigue loading has made them a great fit for retrofitting RC bridge structures (Chaallal et al., 2010; El-Saikaly & Chaallal, 2015-a; El-Saikaly et al., 2018). However, the long-term performance of EB-CFRP strengthened concrete structures can be greatly controlled by the behavior of CFRP-to-concrete bond, with the occurrence of FRP debonding as the most observed failure mode of such structures (Fathi et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2010). According to the related research studies, some of the influencing factors on the bond fatigue behavior at FRP-to-concrete interface include fatigue loading range, FRP and epoxy stiffness, bonded length and FRP width (Fathi et al., 2022). It has been experimentally demonstrated that the fatigue life of FRP-to-concrete bond tends to reduce at higher fatigue load amplitudes (Chalot et al., 2019; Li et al., 2015; Zhu et al., 2016). Also, it has been reported that increasing the bonded length enhances the long-term performance of FRP-to-concrete interface against the debonding failure under fatigue loading conditions (Dai et al., 2005; Diab et al., 2009; Li et al., 2015; Li et al., 2018). Following the experimental studies by Ferrier et al. (2005) and Chalot et al. (2019), it was shown that the bond fatigue behavior was independent of the FRP properties, while Daud et al. (2015) concluded that the FRP stiffness has a dominant effect on the fatigue behavior of FRP-to-concrete bond behavior. An experimental study is conducted herein to further investigate the bond fatigue behavior of CFRP-to-concrete interface with respect to the variables of bonded length and FRP composite type (laminate vs. fabric sheet). To this end, two series of CFRP-to-concrete double-lap bonded joints (Series 1 with CFRP laminate and Series 2 with CFRP sheet) were prepared to undergo fatigue cyclic pull-out load. Moreover, the experimental results are evaluated in terms of bond failure as well as bond-slip behavior and strain distribution along the bonded length to elaborate the fatigue behavior of specimens. Further discussions are presented to compare the performance of specimens with different bonded lengths and CFRP composite types.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Two series (Series 1 and 2) of CFRP-to-concrete bonded joints were prepared for the cyclic double-lap pull-out test. As for the CFRP composite type, CFRP laminate in Series 1 and CFRP fabric sheet in Series 2 were applied to the specimens. Figure 1 shows the experimental set-up for a tested specimen

(specimen with laminate). Also, Table 1 summarises the material properties of specimens. Four different bonded lengths, L_b , of 50 mm, 100 mm, 150 mm, 200 mm were applied in each series. All CFRP laminates were designed to have the same width (b_f) of 25 mm. As for specimens with CFRP sheet, the width was set to be 75 mm. This in fact provides the same FRP stiffness ($t_f f_f b_f$) for both series. Following the concrete compression cylinder testing according to ASTM C39/C39-21 (ASTM, 2021), the average compressive strengths of concrete blocks were attained to be 44 MPa for Series 1 and 44.9 MPa for Series 2. Several strain gauges were installed on the centerline of CFRP sheets to capture the strain distribution, ϵ_i , during load cycles. The strain gauge arrangement for each bonded length, L_b , can also be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Cyclic test set-up and strain gauge arrangement of specimens with CFRP and different bonded lengths: a) double-lap set-up; b) $L_b = 50$ mm; c) $L_b = 100$ mm; d) $L_b = 150$ mm; and e) $L_b = 200$ mm (all dimensions in mm)

Table 1: Material properties of CFRP sheet and epoxy adhesive

Product name	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile elongation (%)	Thickness (mm)
CFRP laminate: SikaCarboDur S512	165	2800	>1.7	1.2
Epoxy adhesive for CFRP laminate: Sikadur -30	4.5	24.8	1	-
CFRP sheet: SikaWrap Hex -103 C (cured with Sikadur -300)	71.7	1110	1.45	1.016
Epoxy adhesive for CFRP sheet: Sikadur -330	3.8	30	1.5	-

As for the application of fatigue cyclic loading, the upper and lower limits (P_{max} and P_{min}) were set to be equal to 65% and 35% of the ultimate monotonic load carrying capacity, P_u , respectively. The specimens were loaded at a frequency rate of 3 Hz up to the maximum 2 million load cycles ($N_{max}=2$ million). In cases where no failure occurred during the cyclic testing, specimens were subjected to post-fatigue monotonic loading (at the rate of 0.5 mm/min) until the debonding failure and their residual load-carrying capacity, $P_{u,r}$, was captured.

Experimental results

Test observations showed that Series 1 specimens (with laminate) failed during cyclic loading whereas Series 2 specimens (with sheet) all survived 2 million load cycles and thereby underwent post-fatigue monotonic loading until the debonding failure. Table 2 presents the test results of specimens during the experiment. Note that N_f is the number of load cycles until failure during the fatigue testing and the specimen label represents, in order the CFRP type (“L” for laminate and “S” for sheet), bonded length and bonded width.

Table 2: Experimental test results

Series	No.	Specimen label	P_u (kN)	P_{max} (kN)	P_{min} (kN)	N_f	$P_{u,r}$ (kN)
Series 1	1	L-50-25	12.1	4.2	7.9	52,980	-
	2	L-100-25	16.7	5.8	10.9	79,684	-
	3	L-150-25	17.9	6.3	11.6	559,470	-
	4	L-200-25	18	6.3	11.7	528,379	-
Series 2	5	S-50-75	23.6	8.3	15.3	>2 million	22.6
	6	S-100-75	27.8	9.7	18.1	>2 million	28.8
	7	S-150-75	27.8	9.7	18.1	>2 million	32
	8	S-200-75	27.8	9.7	18.1	>2 million	29.9

As can be seen, increasing the bonded length overall improved the bond performance in terms of fatigue life, N_f , in Series 1 and residual load-carrying capacity, $P_{u,r}$, in Series 2. It is also noteworthy that the post-fatigue residual capacity of specimens with sheet (Series 2) reached similar values to their corresponding monotonic ultimate load-capacity. This is attributed to the fact that post-fatigue residual resistance was independent of the applied fatigue loads during cycles, which was already confirmed in related studies (Carloni et al., 2012; Li et al., 2015; Yun et al., 2008).

Failure modes

Figure 2 shows the debonding failure patterns of specimens. As can be seen, the fatigue debonding failure of specimens with CFRP laminate occurred majorly within the FRP-to-adhesive interface. This can confirm that the epoxy adhesive underwent fatigue degradation during the cyclic fatigue loading in these specimens. However, the post-fatigue monotonic debonding failure of specimens with CFRP sheet was seen to dominantly occur as a result of concrete cover separation. Indeed, this mode of debonding failure is the most observed failure mode for FRP-to-concrete bonded joints under monotonic loading condition (Chen & Teng, 2001; De Lorenzis et al., 2001; Fathi et al., 2023; Yao et al., 2005).

Bond-slip behavior

The CFRP-to-concrete interface can undergo stiffness degradation under fatigue cyclic loading (Dai et al., 2005). The bond-stress slip at CFRP-to-concrete interface can be determined through the following equations:

$$s_i = \frac{\Delta x_i}{2} (\varepsilon_0 + 2 \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \varepsilon_j + \varepsilon_i) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\tau_i = \frac{t_f E_f}{\Delta x_i} |\Delta \varepsilon_i| \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where s_i is the bond slip, Δx_i is the distance between two constitutive strain gauges and ε_0 is the strain at the free end of CFRP composite which is equal to zero. Also, τ_i is the bond stress, t_f and E_f are the CFRP thickness and CFRP elastic modulus, respectively and $\Delta \varepsilon_i$ is the difference between two consecutive strain gauges.

Error! Reference source not found. and Figure 4 show the bond-slip behavior of Specimen L-150-25 and Specimen S-150-75, respectively, during cyclic loading. As can be seen, the peak cyclic bond stress tends to decrease with increasing load cycles in both specimens. Also, the bond slip has an increasing trend as load cycles increase. This, in fact, results in a fatigue bond degradation during load cycles and leads to the growth of debonding along the bonded length until the occurrence of debonding failure, as appeared in Specimen L-150-25. However, in specimens with CFRP sheet (e.g., Specimen S-150-75), the bond resisted the entire cyclic loading ($N_{max}=2$ million) and failure occurred during the post-fatigue monotonic loading in the form of concrete cover separation. This can be attributed to the greater CFRP-to-concrete width ratio of specimens with sheet (Series 2) in comparison with those bonded with laminate (Series 1), which resulted in a better fatigue performance during the cyclic loading.

Figure 2: Debonding failure patterns of tested specimens

Figure 3: Bond-slip behavior of Specimen L-150-25

Figure 4: Bond-slip behavior of Specimen S-150-25

Effective bond length

The effective bond length is defined as the length after which no significant enhanced bond strength can be achieved under monotonic loading (Ben Oueddou et al., 2009; Fathi et al., 2023). In the case of cyclic loading, the effective bond length is the active stress-transfer zone along the bonded length and can be established through the strain distribution during load cycles (Li et al., 2015). Figure 5 shows the cyclic strain distribution of Specimen L-150-25 (specimen bonded with laminate). As can be seen, the average bonded length in which the strain distribution occurs during load cycles, namely effective bond length, can be estimated to be in the range between 100 mm and 120 mm. As for specimen with CFRP sheet, the post-fatigue monotonic strain distribution of Specimen S-150-75 is drawn in Figure 6. It can be observed that strain distribution at load cycles near the ultimate monotonic load (i.e., at 0.9-0.99 $P_{u,r}$) lies in the range between 50 mm and 100 mm.

Figure 5: Strain distribution of Specimen L-150-25 during load cycles

Figure 6: Strain distribution of Specimen S-150-75 under post-fatigue monotonic loading

CONCLUSION

An experimental investigation was carried to investigate the bond fatigue behavior of CFRP-to-concrete interface during cyclic pull-out tests. The effects of CFRP type and bond-length were evaluated. Based on the experimental observations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The main failure mode of specimens with laminate occurred in the form of debonding within FRP-to-adhesive interface during cyclic loading, while specimens with CFRP sheet failed due to concrete cover separation under post-fatigue monotonic loading.
- Increasing the bond length overall enhanced the fatigue and post-fatigue monotonic performance of specimens in terms of fatigue life and post-fatigue residual resistance, respectively. However, during the post-fatigue monotonic loading, increasing the bonded length after the effective bond length did not enhance the bond strength of specimens with CFRP sheet.
- The application of CFRP sheet proved to have a better bond performance in comparison with CFRP laminate with equivalent width in terms of bond-fatigue life. Indeed, all specimens bonded with sheet endured the entire cyclic loading while specimens with CFRP laminate underwent fatigue failure during cyclic loading.
- The post-fatigue monotonic residual capacity of specimens was seen to remain unaffected by the fatigue cyclic loads and was therefore similar to the corresponding bond monotonic capacity.
- The CFRP-to-concrete bond tends to undergo fatigue degradation, which can be represented by an increase in the bond slip and a decrease in the bond stress during load cycles.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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